

**Treatment of auditory hallucinations in schizophrenia with bilateral
theta-burst stimulation**

TBS-AH

Study registration: NCT02670291

(Protocol Version V2.4 15.02.2019)

FINAL ANALYSIS

Statistical Analysis Plan

Version: V 1.0, 30.01.2024

Valid from: Last date of Signature (Sponsor)

Author: Peter Martus	
Date: 30.1.2024	Signature:
<hr/>	
Sponsor (represented by PI Christian Plewnia):	
Date: 02.02.24	Signature:

Abbreviations	3
1 Introduction.....	4
2 Database and Data Transfer to Statistical Centre	4
3 Analysis Populations and Blind Review	5
4 Definition of Endpoints	5
4.1 Primary Endpoint	5
4.2 Secondary Endpoints	6
4.2.1 Efficacy	6
4.2.2 Compliance.....	6
4.2.3 Adverse Events	6
4.3 Demographic data and other characteristics	6
4.3.1 Sociodemographic data and study centre	6
4.3.2 Vital signs.....	6
4.3.3 Disease Severity, anamnesis and status at baseline	6
4.3.4 Description of stimulation parameters	6
4.3.5 Laboratory variables.....	7
4.3.6 Imaging	7
4.4 Medication.....	7
5 Statistical Analyses	7
5.1 Analysis of Primary Endpoint.....	7
5.1.1 Confirmatory Analysis	7
5.1.2 Sensitivity Analyses	7
5.2 Analyses of Secondary Endpoints.....	7
5.3 Adverse Events	7
5.4 Descriptive analyses	8
5.5 Variable Transformations and derived variables	8
5.6 Missing Data	8
5.7 Exploratory multiple regression analysis.....	8
5.8 Subgroup analyses.....	8

Abbreviations

AE	Adverse Event
AvH	auditory verbal hallucinations
CRF	Case Report Form
CRO	Contract Research Organisation
cTBS	continuous theta burst stimulation
GAF	Global Assessment of Functioning Scale
GCP	Good Clinical Practice
CGI-I	Clinical Global Impression Scale
ID	Identification (code)
IKEAB	Institut für Klinische Epidemiologie und angewandte Biometrie (Dpt. for Clinical Epidemiology and Applied Biostatistics)
ITT	Intention to Treat (Population)
MedDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities
PANSS	Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale
PP	Per Protocol (Population)
Pt.	Patient
PSYRATS-AH	auditory hallucinations subscale of the Psychotic Symptom Rating Scales
rTMS	repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation
SAE	Serious Adverse Event
SAF	Safety (Population)
SAP	Statistical Analysis Plan
ZKS	Centre for clinical studies, University Tübingen

1 Introduction

Auditory verbal hallucinations (AvH), a cardinal feature of schizophrenia, are often severely distressing, interfere heavily with daily life functioning and increase the risk for violence and suicide. The available pharmacological and psychotherapeutic treatment is often insufficient. Non-invasive brain stimulation, particularly repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation (rTMS) represents a promising treatment alternative. However, this technique is quite time-consuming, which can have a negative impact on patients' adherence to treatment and can result in high costs for the healthcare system. A substantial reduction of stimulation time can be achieved by applying a different stimulation paradigm, the continuous theta burst stimulation (cTBS).

The objective of this randomized double-blind clinical trial was to show superiority of cTBS compared to sham stimulation and to investigate safety aspects. Patients were randomized (only centre as stratum) with a 1:1 ratio either to verum or sham condition. Study protocol comprised 15 sessions of bilateral stimulation of the temporoparietal cortices in a period of 3 weeks.

This is the statistical analysis plan for the final analysis of the study *TBS-AH: Treatment of auditory hallucinations in schizophrenia with bilateral theta-burst stimulation* which has been designed as an adaptive trial and which has passed an interim analysis with sample size adaption at 29th of July 2020.

The initially proposed sample size resulted in a total number (stage I and II) of 86 patients (power of 90%) which was based on a pilot study of our group (33) in which the PSYRATS-AH scale were available at baseline and after 3 weeks of stimulation. The delta post-pre therapy was calculated. The difference in delta between verum and sham group was 5.25 and the pooled standard deviation was 5.42. This led to a standardized difference of 0.97 but we conservatively assumed that the effect size of 0.70 is observed after step I, which would have led to a p-value of 0.0216 in step 1 and to a p-value of 0.1758 in step 2.

In the interim analysis a one-sided p-value of 0.0335 was observed. This led to the decision to prolong the study with changed sample size of additional 78 evaluable patients and estimated 94 patients to be recruited taking into account 12% drop outs and degrees of freedom for centre and baseline.

The primary endpoint Primary outcome is the change of PSYRATS-AH after 3 weeks of cTBS as compared to sham treatment and the primary analysis population is the ITT.

The analysis will focus on the primary endpoint, secondary endpoints, exploratory analyses, and safety. It will be done after closure of the databank. The SAP of this analysis is provided by the study statistician.

2 Database and Data Transfer to Statistical Centre

Primary data were obtained in seven different study centres. One centre dropped out very early during the study but provides two cases to this analysis which have been documented sufficiently. CRFs were submitted from the study centres to the documentation centre (IKEaB, Dpt. of Clinical Epidemiology and applied Biostatistics, Tübingen) and data were entered into the clinical database system Koordobas according to the requirements of GCP. Monitoring was performed by the ZKS (Zentrum für Klinische Studien) Tübingen. Only monitored data will be used for the analysis. Databank closure is defined with the availability

of monitored data. AEs/SAEs were entered in the same database without using a classification scheme (like e.g. MedDRA).

Data were anonymised for the documentation centre, only numerical patient ID codes were transferred. From the Koordobas database a data export was performed to SPSS format (via SAS format) to produce statistically analysable data files.

3 Analysis Populations and Blind Review

Following the study protocol, the primary analysis population is the ITT (Intent to Treat) Population. This means that each patient with baseline assessment and at least one TMS treatment will be included). Multiple imputation using baseline values and all available data during treatment will be used as predictors in the imputation step. Three thousand imputation samples will be used.

In a blind review, assignment to the populations will be performed. The criteria will be documented and applied analogously to the interim analysis, which guarantees that patients from the interim analysis remain in the same population for the final analysis. The Per Protocol population (PP) will also be defined before the analysis. The data management will provide a list of relevant variables, which allow the assignment of populations without breaking the blinding of treatment. The clinical partners will provide a list of variables necessary for the blind review. This list will be checked by the study statistician regarding completeness from statistical point of view and avoidance of accidental unblinding.

The following list gives the preliminary criteria for the assignment of the analysis populations.

Per Protocol (PP):

Includes all patients with no deviations from inclusion / exclusion criteria, documented PSYRATS-AH values at baseline, participation of at least 80% of 15 i.e. 12 treatment sessions, stable antipsychotic medication during the treatment phase, and documented PSYRATS-AH at the end of treatment.

Intention to treat (ITT):

Includes all PP patients and additionally each patient with baseline documentation of the primary endpoint and at least one stimulation session.

Safety Population (SAF):

The safety population consists of all patients, which received at least one treatment session.

4 Definition of Endpoints

4.1 Primary Endpoint

Primary outcome is the change of PSYRATS-AH after 3 weeks (last treatment session) of cTBS as compared to sham treatment. This score has a range from 0 to 44.

4.2 Secondary Endpoints

4.2.1 Efficacy

Secondary endpoints regarding efficacy are:

- The rate of responders to cTBS compared to sham treatment. Treatment response is defined as the reduction of the PSYRATS-AH score by 25% or more
- Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) for the measurement of symptom severity in schizophrenia
- PANSS item 3 (auditory hallucinations)
- Global Assessment of Functioning Scale (GAF) to evaluate the effect of treatment on more general measures of psychosocial functioning
- Clinical Global Impression Scale (CGI-I) to monitor and quantify treatment progress / response.

All measures were planned to be obtained before treatment period, after each week of treatment (V5, V10, V15) as well as 1, 3 and 6 months after end of treatment period. For each of the endpoints a linear mixed model including all time points with time vs treatment interaction (and treatment, time, study centre as factors) will be calculated.

4.2.2 Compliance

This will be assessed using the number of TBS sessions (absolute number, \geq / $<$ 80%).

4.2.3 Adverse Events

Adverse events will be analysed in the Safety Population as described in section 5.

4.3 Demographic data and other characteristics

4.3.1 Sociodemographic data and study centre

A description of the sample including (age, gender, handedness, years of education, study centre) will be provided.

4.3.2 Vital signs

A description of the sample including (body height, body weight). Additionally the smoking behaviour (Fagerström scale) will be reported.

4.3.3 Disease Severity, anamnesis and status at baseline

A descriptive analysis of baseline PSYRATS-AH values and all secondary variables will be provided. Additionally, the following anamnestic variables will be evaluated: disease duration (time since first diagnosis and time since first AvH at baseline).

4.3.4 Description of stimulation parameters

The following parameters will be analysed: Resting motor threshold, stimulation intensity as percentage of resting motor threshold. These analyses will be done separately for right and left hemisphere.

4.3.5 Laboratory variables

N.A.

4.3.6 Imaging

N.A.

4.4 Medication

The use of antipsychotic medication at baseline and the end of treatment will be analysed using frequency tabulations. Changes in medication will be identified as protocol violations. Additionally the chlorpromazine equivalent dose will be analysed.

5 Statistical Analyses

5.1 Analysis of Primary Endpoint

5.1.1 Confirmatory Analysis

The primary analysis will be done as an analysis of covariance with baseline PSYRATS-AH as continuous covariate and treatment arm as factor. Additionally, the stratification factor “study centre” will be included. The primary analysis refers to the significance test with H0: *No difference between treatment and control* and H1: *Treatment superior to control*. The level of significance will be $0.00380/0.03350 = 0.113$ (one-sided) according to the adaptive design of Bauer and Köhne.

5.1.2 Sensitivity Analyses

Sensitivity analyses for the primary endpoint will be done using the PP and the complete case population. In both analyses no imputation is necessary as outcome values are available for each subject. The method will be identical to the primary analysis (baseline adjusted ANCOVA with study centre as nuisance factors).

5.2 Analyses of Secondary Endpoints

Secondary analyses of continuous endpoints with baseline values will be done in the same way as the analysis of the primary endpoint, i.e. baseline adjusted ANCOVA with study centre as nuisance variable and study arm as relevant factor. Categorical endpoints will be analysed using logistic regression models with study centre as nuisance variable and study arm as relevant factor. No sensitivity analyses will be done for secondary endpoints.

5.3 Adverse Events

Adverse events will be analysed using line listings and tables in the safety population. The following types of tables will be given:

Table 1 Frequency of patients with at least one adverse event according to study arm

Table 2 Frequency of adverse events according to study arm

Table 3 Frequency of patients with at least one severe adverse event according to study arm

Table 4 Frequency of severe adverse events according to study arm

Listing 1 Listing of all AEs including patient ID, natural language description of the event, start date, stop date, severity, outcome.

5.4 Descriptive analyses

These analyses include all variables primary and secondary endpoints, demography, anamnesis, status at baseline, and medication. Tabulations will include descriptive parameters for quantitative variables (means, medians, standard deviations, quartiles, and absolute and relative frequencies for categorical variables. Tabulations will be given for the total sample and separately according to study arms.

5.5 Variable Transformations and derived variables

Quantitative variables will be assessed for normal distribution. If necessary, log transformations will be applied. The dose of antipsychotic medication will be harmonised using the chlorpromazine equivalents.

5.6 Missing Data

Multiple imputation using baseline values and all available data during treatment will be used as predictors in the imputation step. Three thousand imputation samples will be used. This will be done for the primary endpoint and the secondary efficacy endpoint.

5.7 Exploratory multiple regression analysis

In a multiple regression model, additionally to treatment arm, baseline, and study centre the following variables will be checked for prognostic values: gender, age, disease duration, antipsychotic medication, and stimulation intensity. Interaction with study arm will be examined.

5.8 Subgroup analyses

Planned subgroup analysis will be done according to gender and age (median split). In case of significant interactions in the multiple regression analysis, additional subgroup analyses will be defined.